

On the Proof-of-Work Puzzle Hardness in Bitcoin Blockchain

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Abstract

The blockchain is a secure, decentralized, distributed ledger which stores transaction in a chain of blocks. Bitcoin uses the distributed public ledger for storing transactional records. Bitcoin uses proof-of-work to mine blocks which correspond to compute hashes to solve a cryptographic puzzle. Computing power is becoming cheaper exponentially. In this paper, we inspect how bitcoin tackles the growing hashing power available in the network to maintain its consistency.

1. Introduction:

The blockchain is a digital, distributed, decentralized, non-tamperable list of records in which transactions are added in a chronological chain of blocks. The first application of blockchain is bitcoin [1]. Bitcoin is the first digital currency which had tackled the double-spending problem with no central trusted authority in a trustless environment. Bitcoin uses proof-of-work for its consensus algorithm to ensure that each participating node has the same replica of the blockchain. Proof-of-Work is a computational intensive cryptographic puzzle to be solved by miners who append new blocks to blockchain in exchange for bitcoins as an incentive.

Since computing power is growing exponentially at a cheaper cost in accordance with Moore’s law. Bitcoin has inherently embedded that its proof-of-work puzzle gets harder with time to counter the effect of computational power growth on its mining algorithm. This paper explores the underlying mechanism responsible for increasing hardness of bitcoin hashing puzzle with time.

The rest of the document is formulated as follows. Section 2 will give system model followed by problem formulation in section 3. Section 4 shows Analytical Results and in section 5, we will conclude our research work.

2. System Model:

Let there be n miners in our Blockchain network S . The i^{th} node has local Blockchain B_i such that block b_j contains the hash of block b_{j-1} . Where Blockchain is a chain of blocks such that each block has the block header and transactional data.

The block header stores the cryptographic hash of the previous block, timestamp, nonce and Merkle root of transactional data. While the transactional data is stored in the form of Merkle tree. The transactions are hashed, hashes are paired, again hashed and paired until we get the Merkle root of the Merkle tree.

Figure 1: Simplified bitcoin blockchain

Figure 2: The difficulty and hash rate of bitcoin (Data collected from bitcoin.info/charts)

5. Conclusion and Future Work:

In this paper, we explored the puzzle hardness of proof-of-work of the bitcoin blockchain. We inspected that difficulty to mine a block is increasing based on computational power available on the bitcoin network. The bitcoin processes seven transactions per second on average. With the increasing computational power of miners and the increasing difficulty to mine blocks, the time to mine a block is still at its equilibrium level of ten minutes on average. The increase in transaction speed, scalability as well as consistency and reliability of bitcoin network is critical to its growth and sustainability. There is a need to research and implement algorithms for increasing transaction speed while keeping the consistency of bitcoin blockchain sustained.

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[REFERENCES]

- [1] Nakamoto, Satoshi. "Bitcoin: A peer-to-peer electronic cash system." (2008).
- [2] Gramoli, Vincent. "From blockchain consensus back to Byzantine consensus." *Future Generation Computer Systems* (2017).
- [3] Böhme, Sascha. *Analysis of Bitcoin as a peer-to-peer network for international payments*. Diss. Massachusetts Institute of Technology, 2014.
- [4] O'Dwyer, Karl J., and David Malone. "Bitcoin mining and its energy footprint." (2014): 280-285.